

**ANALYSIS OF THE TECHNOLOGIES FOR ELIMINATING THE
COMPLICATIONS IN GAS AND GASCONDENSATE WELLS**

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Enter

Currently, a large number of wells in gas and gas condensate fields are characterized by the accumulation of liquid at the bottom, followed by spontaneous expansion. This leads to the cessation of gas production from the well, which leads to large losses of recoverable gas and, as a result, the final gas recovery rate is not achieved. According to forecasts of experts in the gas production industry, by 2030, the number of wells stopped due to the accumulation of liquid at the bottom of the well will make up 50% of the total well fund. This problem is especially relevant at the final stage of field development, when formation pressure and well productivity decrease. Therefore, it is urgent to search for solutions to combat complications during gas production in gas and gas condensate fields.

The main part

It is dedicated to the creation of technology and technical means of mechanized use of flooded gas wells, research of developed technical solutions.

As part of the works, the process of accumulation of liquid at the bottom of gas wells is considered, as well as the world experience of eliminating complications

arising during the development of gas and gas condensate deposits is studied, and the problem of water removal from the well bottom is not solved. The direction of finding li is chosen.

Study of pumping equipment and technology for the use of wells with a large amount of mechanical impurities.

Research is being conducted on the modification of small-sized open-type wheels to determine the energy efficiency of their use for extracting high-gas well products. The results of the technology of mechanized pumping of flooded gas wells with the help of small-scale pumping equipment developed in the presented scientific research work are given.

1. Analysis of existing technologies to combat self-extinguishing of gas production wells and research on the process of gas well flooding during the post-operation phase.

2. Development of technical and technological solutions for the mechanized method of removing water from the bottom of gas wells using submersible pump equipment.

3. Development of pumping equipment for the use of wells with a lot of gas and mechanical impurities in the extracted products.

4. A lot phase products pump with release for work developed equipment experimental studies transfer

5. Well of the equipment technological parameters in the change watered down gas from the layer removable products flow research to do

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Summary

From the research results presented above, it became clear that the following changes should be made in the centrifugal pumps currently used in liquid extraction.

1. Study of the design of a labyrinth-screw pump for driving multiphase products with a high degree of dispersion of the gas-liquid mixture in multi-entry screw

channels. The studied design makes it possible to expand the range of technical operating conditions of the pump and to simplify its production compared to existing screw and labyrinth pumps.

2. The technology of using wells with high-content mechanical mixtures with a reversible working chamber to drive multiphase products with a solid phase concentration of up to 50% by volume, superior to existing similar technical solutions. learning

3. Proposing a new technical solution based on centrifugal-vortex forces, researching a small-sized pump with a semi-open working stage for the use of self-extinguishing gas wells with water accumulated at the bottom of the well.

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